

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

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Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABDULLA bearing USN6SU19ML001 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ALFIYA Ubearing USN6SU19ML002 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANANDHU KRISHNA K Mbearing USN6SU19ML003 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANSWAR AHAMMED K Pbearing USN6SU19ML004 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANURAG Sbearing USN6SU19ML005 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANUSHREE A Vbearing USN6SU19ML006 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms FATHIMA REHAN bearing USN6SU19ML007 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms GEETHU Pbearing USN6SU19ML008 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JIJISHA Pbearing USN6SU19ML009 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms KAVYASHREE A C bearing USN6SU19ML010 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms KRITHI Kbearing USN6SU19ML011 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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**This is to certify that Mr/Ms MARIYOLA DOLLY FERRAObearing
USN6SU19ML012 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical
science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab
Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020**

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MEHA SAJI bearing USN6SU19ML013 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED ASHIK K Sbearing USN6SU19ML014 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED JAZEEL VKbearing USN6SU19ML015 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED SHIBILI V bearing USN6SU19ML016 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHSIN P Mbearing USN6SU19ML017 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIMRAH NOORJHAN bearing USN6SU19ML018 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SANCHITHA SHETTY bearing USN6SU19ML019 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHILPA BABU bearing USN6SU19ML020 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms THUPTEN DHARGEY bearing USN6SU19ML021 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms YADHUKRISHNAN K Mbearing USN6SU19ML022 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas institute of medical science and research centre Mangalore in the first Semester of the BSc. Medical Lab Technician programme for the academic year 2019-2020

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